

Peridinium quadridentatum (Dinophyceae) is an occasional daily diurnal surface forming algal bloom species in Veracruz, Mexico

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Abstract

It has been 19 years since the first bloom of the non-toxic dinoflagellate *Peridinium quadridentatum* was recorded in Veracruz, Mexico. Since then, recurrent blooms have occurred in Veracruz central coast, specifically in the port of Veracruz and Boca del Río, the most important cities with an extended urban coastal zone. Prior to the first reported *P. quadridentatum* blooms, the cause of discoloured water in southwestern Gulf of Mexico were recurrent blooms of the toxic dinoflagellate *Karenia brevis*. Though not toxic, *P. quadridentatum* blooms cause hypoxia and significant water discolouration which is unappealing to beachgoers. We analysed the information generated through 13 years of observations of *P. quadridentatum* blooms in different studies in Veracruz including: occurrences, annual dynamics, and diel behaviour of the species. *Peridinium quadridentatum* blooms at the beginning of the rainy season when salinity decreases, with warm water temperature, with cell abundances increasing during the day and under a relatively high Redfield ratio of dissolved nutrient concentrations where N is not limiting. We believe that the benthic-planktonic habitat and the vertical migration of this dinoflagellate is favourable for the daytime blooms. We characterized the blooms of *P. quadridentatum* as an occasional daily diurnal surface (ODDS) forming harmful algal bloom species in Veracruz.

Keywords: benthic microalgae, *Blixaea*, dinotom, Gulf of Mexico, *quinquecorne*

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Introduction

Peridinium quadridentatum (Stein) Hansen is a thecate dinoflagellate characterized by the possession of four thick spines at the hypotheca (Fig. 1). Specifically, the spines are in pairs on each antapical plate, though a variety exists which exhibits only three spines: one on the first antapical and two on the second antapical plate (Aké-Castillo and Vázquez, 2011). *Peridinium quadridentatum* belongs to the family Kryptoperidiniaceae (Gottschling *et al.*, 2017), whose members utilize a tertiary endosymbiont derived from a diatom to carry out photosynthesis. This species was formerly known as *Heterocapsa quadridentata* Stein, which has been synonymised to *Peridinium quinquecorne* Abé and *Protoperidinium quinquecorne* (Abé) Balech. Recently Gottschling *et al.* (2017) erected the new genus based in the type of *Peridinium quinquecorne* and transferred the species: *Blixaea quinquecornis* (Abé) Gottschling, giving priority to this type over the older *H. quadridentata* type, arguing that the endosymbiont has not been verified in organisms under the name of *P. quadridentatum*.

Peridinium quadridentatum is non-toxic, widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2021). It is considered a harmful species because it can cause oxygen depletion, increases turbidity, and discolouration of the water creating unaesthetic conditions for visitors at beaches (Okolodkov *et al.*, 2016; Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.*, 2021). *Peridinium quadridentatum* was first recorded forming a bloom in Veracruz, Mexico in 2002 (Barón-Campis *et al.*, 2005). Since then, recurrent blooms have been recorded in at least one location along

the State of Veracruz coast every year (Aké-Castillo *et al.*, 2013; Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.*, 2015; unpublished data). These blooms appear to have replaced the *Karenia brevis* blooms that formerly occurred in the region (Aké-Castillo *et al.*, 2014; Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.*, 2015).

Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.* (2019a) proposed a conceptual model for describing the blooms of *P. quadridentatum* in Veracruz. This model includes the preferential uptake of certain forms of limiting nutrients and general environmental conditions that favor the blooms. Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.* (2019b) further studied the short-term responses of this species to high-frequency environmental fluctuations and demonstrated the bloom population vertically migrates up and down in the water column on a diel basis. The objective of this work was to construct a more complete descriptive model describing the dynamics of the *P. quadridentatum* blooms often observed off Veracruz, Mexico, and along the southwestern Gulf of Mexico generally.

Fig. 1. Microphotograph (SEM) of the dinoflagellate *Peridinium quadridentatum* from Veracruz, Mexico.

Material and Methods

For the conceptual characterization of *P. quadridentatum* blooms in Veracruz, we used the information generated in previous works: Okolodkov *et al.* (2007, 2016); Aké-Castillo *et al.* (2013, 2014); Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.* (2015, 2019a, b).

Results and Discussion

The literature review enabled us to summarise aspects of the ecology of *Peridinium quadridentatum* blooms in Veracruz as follows:

- 1) The species is present all year in some sites along the coast of Veracruz-Boca del Río municipalities.
- 2) Blooms are evident as discoloured (reddish-brown) surface patches that last for short periods of time over the course of the year.
- 3) Blooms occur during the first months of the rainy season (July-August) reaching around 30 thousand cells per millilitre.
- 4) Blooms occur when concentrations of nitrogen (ammonium and nitrates) are high and phosphate (orthophosphate) is limiting, i.e. under relatively high N:P ratios.
- 5) Blooms are most apparent during the daylight hours with cells densities on the surface increasing during the morning, reaching a maximum concentration in the afternoon ($> 3,000 \text{ cell mL}^{-1}$). Surface cell concentrations begin decreasing toward sunset with the lowest concentration observed at night ($< 1,000 \text{ cell mL}^{-1}$). Concomitantly, *P. quadridentatum* abundances in bottom substrates (coral rubble, macroalgae, seaweed, and the seagrass *Thalassia testudinum*)

increase during night and decrease during the day.

6) Blooms occur from one to four days.

7) Surface blooms may occur every year at some locations.

A further breakdown of what is known about the duration and physical location of the bloom is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Peridinium quadridentatum* bloom characteristics in Veracruz, Mexico. “Occasional” is defined as blooms occurring one to five times in a year in different locations. “Daily” indicates blooms lasting one to four days. “Diurnal” denotes blooms observed during the day. “Surface” indicates surface blooms that discoloured the water.

Bloom characteristic	References						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Occasional	✓			✓		✓	
Daily		✓	✓		✓		✓
Diurnal		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Surface	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓

1) Okolodkov *et al.*, 2007; 2) Okolodkov *et al.*, 2016; 3) Aké-Castillo *et al.*, 2013; 4) Aké-Castillo *et al.*, 2014; 5) Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.*, 2015; 6) Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.*, 2019a; 7) Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.*, 2019b.

Data specifically documenting how the diel vertical migration pattern of *P. quadridentatum* affects surface cell concentrations are shown in Fig. 2. According to this information, we characterized the blooms as an occasional daily diurnal surface harmful algal bloom (ODDS-HAB) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Diel variation in the surface cell concentrations of *Peridinium quadridentatum*. Red line indicates increase/decrease of cell concentration during a three-day bloom period.

Although the species is present all year in the coasts of Veracruz, it maintains low cell densities most of the months. Contrary to other HAB species around the world, the blooms of *P. quadridentatum* in Veracruz are of short duration (from one to four days). For example, the blooms of *Karenia brevis* (C.C. Davis) Gert Hansen & Moestrup (Tominack *et al.*, 2020) and *Pyrodinium bahamense* Plate (Gárate-Lizárraga *et al.*, 2013), can last several weeks or months. Although ODDS-HAB of *P. quadridentatum* in Veracruz may occur at the beginning of the rainy season, they also can occur occasionally from October to January after the events of cold fronts that affect this region in the Gulf of Mexico.

We believe that large populations of *P. quadridentatum* develop at the bottom, as other blooming benthic dinoflagellates do, such as *Prorocentrum* and *Ostreopsis* (Shears and Ross 2009; Zou *et al.*, 2020). This would occur prior to the rainy season. The initiation of the surface blooms of the species at the beginning of the rainy season may be triggered by the decrease of seawater salinity. The benthic-planktonic condition of the species (Horstmann, 1980; Okolodkov *et al.*, 2016),

is a property that favours the daily dynamics of the blooms, allowing the species to migrate into the water column. If migration by itself is a possible explanation for the blooms, the populations during the rainy seasons would take advantage of the surface condition at daylight hours, for example higher light intensity or availability of a limiting nutrient (Katano *et al.* 2011). This could explain the diurnal changes in water colour and surface vanishing during the night-time.

Other possible explanation is that local hydrodynamics may be concentrating and dispersing blooms in a diurnal cycling. For example, stratification and wind force, maintain surface blooms of *Lingulodinium polyedra* (Ruiz-de la Torre *et al.*, 2013). The ODDS blooms of *P. quadridentatum* in Veracruz have occasionally been observed in elongated patches parallel to the coastal zone between the breakwaters and rarely outside these areas, suggesting cell accumulation due to the presence of convective cells, i.e. Langmuir cells (Evans and Taylor, 1980).

In any case, the end of the surface bloom could be the result of decreasing population, staying some days on the bottom to recover cell density, and blooming again in the following weeks. The clarification of the life history of *P. quadridentatum* and the possible relation with hydrodynamic processes will be a key for understanding its blooms.

The characterization of blooms of *P. quadridentatum* recorded in Veracruz, Mexico (ODDS-HAB), are consistent with reports of blooms of this species in other parts of the world (Horstmann, 1980; Trigueros and Orive, 2000). The conceptual characterization for blooms of *P. quadridentatum* can be

applied in general for the species or other species that behave similarly to synthesize our knowledge of the ecology of this type of bloom dynamics.

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References

- Aké-Castillo, J.A. and Vázquez, G. (2011). *Acta Bot. Mex.* 94, 125-140.
- Aké-Castillo, J.A., Rodríguez-Gómez, C.F., Campos-Bautista, G. (2013). Libro de resúmenes, II Congreso de la Sociedad Mexicana para el Estudio de los Florecimientos Algales Nocivos, p. 23.
- Aké-Castillo, J.A., Okolodkov, Y.B., Rodríguez-Gómez, C.F., Campos-Bautista, G. (2014). Golfo de México. Contaminación e impacto ambiental: diagnóstico y tendencias, 133-146.
- Evans, G.T., Taylor, F.J.R. (1980). *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 25, 840-845.
- Gárate-Lizárraga, I., Pérez-Cruz, B., Díaz-Ortiz, J. A., Alarcón-Tacuba, M.A., *et al.*, (2013). *CICIMAR Oceanides* 28, 37-42.
- Gottschling, M., Calasan, A.Z., Kretschmann, J., Gu, H. (2017). *Phytotaxa* 306, 296-300.
- Horstmann, U. (1980). *J. Phycol.* 16, 481-485.
- Katano, T., Yoshida, M., Yamaguchi, S., Hamada, T., *et al.*, (2011). *Plankton Benthos Res.* 6, 92-100.
- Okolodkov, Y.B., Campos-Bautista, G., Gárate-Lizárraga, I., González-González, J.A.G., *et al.*, (2007). *Aquat. Microb. Ecol.* 47, 223-237.
- Okolodkov, Y.B., Campos-Bautista, G., Gárate-Lizárraga, I. (2016). *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 108, 289-296.
- Rodríguez-Gómez, C.F., Aké-Castillo, J.A., Campos-Bautista, G., Okolodkov, Y.B. (2015). *E-Bios* 2, 178-191.
- Rodríguez-Gómez, C.F., Vázquez, G., Aké-Castillo, J.A., Band-Schmidt, C.J., Moreno-Casasola, P. (2019a). *Estuar. Coast. Shelf. Sci.* 230, 106412.
- Rodríguez-Gómez, C.F., Aké-Castillo, J.A., Vázquez, G. (2019b). *J. Coast. Res.* SI 92, 22-32.
- Rodríguez-Gómez, C.F., Vázquez, G., Maya-Lastra, C.A., Aké-Castillo, J.A., *et al.*, (2021). *Mar. Biol.* 168, 29.
- Ruiz-de la Torre, M.C., Maske, H., Ochoa, J., Almeda-Jauregui, C.O. (2013). *PLoS ONE* 8, e58958.
- Shears, N.T., Ross, P.M. (2009). *Harmful Algae* 8, 916-925.

Tominack, S.A., Coffey, K.Z., Yoskowitz, D., Sutton, G., Wetz, M.S. (2020). PLoS ONE 15, e0239309.

Trigueros, J.M. and Orive, E. (2000). J. Plank. Res. 22, 969-986.

Zou, J., Li, Q., Lu, S., Dong, Y., *et al.*, (2020). Mar. Pollut. Bull. 158, 111313.

